

International Peer Review Journal

p-ISSN 1817-5562

e-ISSN 1998-037X (Online)

CD-ROM ISSN 1998-0361

The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine

The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health

Volume 5 Number 2 August 2009

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journal published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer -review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list .The first tow issues of this journal appeared under the title of al Karkh journal of Medicine

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Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

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Supplement: Cancer in Iraq: 2000-2005

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Frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Little is known about the frequency of various childhood cancers in Iraq. The aim of this paper is to report the frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq in the largest series of Iraqi patients with cancer.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 5049 cases of cancers occurred in children under 14 years of age accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results: Leukemia is by far the commonest childhood cancer in Iraq accounting for 33% of childhood cancers. The top 10 childhood cancers were : leukemias, Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye (retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of testis and ovary.

Conclusion: The pattern of childhood cancer in Iraq is slightly different from the patterns in other countries. Higher frequency of leukemias than most other countries.

Keywords: Childhood, Cancer, Iraq, Pattern

Introduction

Childhood cancers (age at diagnosis: 0-14 years) comprise a variety of malignancies, with incidence varying worldwide by age, sex, ethnicity and geography. Substantial regional differences in the incidence of childhood cancer have been reported. The incidence may vary according to gender, age, race, and ethnicity [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Little is known about childhood cancer in Iraq. The aim of this paper is to describe the pattern of childhood cancer in Iraq. These research findings are useful for prioritizing future childhood cancer research needs. The aim of this paper is to report the frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq in the largest series of Iraqi patients with cancer.

Patients and methods

In largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004) 5049 cases of cancers occurred in children under 14 years of age accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results

Leukemia is by far the commonest childhood cancer in Iraq accounting for 33% of childhood cancers. The top 10 childhood cancers were : leukemias, Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) , central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye (retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of testis and ovary. Cancers of the livers ranked 11th in the list accounting for less than 1% of childhood cancers.

The top 10 childhood cancers in males as shown in table-1 were: leukemias, Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) , central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye (retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of ovary.

	No (%)	Males	Females
Leukemia	1675 (33%)	999	676
NHL	834(16.5%)	537	297
Brain & CNS	786(15.6%)	459	327
Hodgkin lymphoma	262 (5%)	193	69
Kidney	246(4.9%)	135	111
Bone	227(4.5%)	127	100
Eye	173(3.4%)	102	71
Soft tissues	159 (3.1%)	91	68
Adrenal	106 (2.1%)	55	51
Testis/Ovary	90 (1.8%)	26	64
Liver	45 (0.9%)	23	22

Table (1): The pattern of childhood cancers

The top 10 childhood cancers in females as shown in table-1 were : Leukemias, central nervous system neoplasms Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) , central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye

(retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of testis and ovary.

Discussion

The frequency of malignant neoplasms in children has been found to vary among countries. For example, in children in Canada, the United States, and Europe, the three most common cancers are leukemias, tumors of the central nervous system (CNST), and lymphomas [7,8,9], whereas in children in Latin America, the order of frequencies is distinct: leukemias are still in first place, with lymphomas being more common than are CNST [8,10,11,12]. In other countries such as Nigeria, Malawi, and Egypt, lymphomas are the principal neoplasias [8].

The percentage of cases of each type of neoplasm in relation to the total number of cancers is also different. In the developed countries, the percentages for leukemias range between 30 and 37%; for CNST, between 18 and 27%; and for lymphomas, between 7 and 12% [7, 8, 9]. In Latin America, the percentages for leukemias are between 27 and 44%; of lymphomas, between 13 and 22%; and of CNST, between 10 and 19% [28, 10, 11, 12]. In African countries, the percentages of lymphomas range between 30 and 64% [8]. In Asian countries such as Japan and China, the percentages of leukemias have been found to be between 30 and 40%; of CNST, between 12 and 20%; and of lymphomas, between 10 and 20% [8].

During the decade 1968-1977 a total of 1488 cases of neoplasms was registered

in Slovakia in children aged 0-14 years .The most common malignancies were leukemias (28.2%), tumors of nervous system (23.9%), lymphomas (14.9%) and Wilm's tumors of kidney (6.7%) [4].

In Poland the most frequent childhood cancers include leukemia, which accounts for (28%) of cancer cases, lymphoma (14.3%) and CNS tumors (16.3%). Neoplasms of the hematopoietic system (leukemias and lymphomas) account for about 42% of all childhood cancers. Malignant lymphomas, bone tumors and germinal tumors are more frequently diagnosed in Poland, but the incidence of central nervous system tumors is lower than in other countries [6].Figure-1 shows the pattern of childhood cancers in 4 countries.

The study of the frequency of cancer in children not only is of interest to the clinical physician because it helps him/her to establish the pre-testing probability for a child suspected of having cancer [13], but also is of interest to the personnel in charge of the planning and programming of the medical attention for these children, as pertains to the assignment of human resources (physicians, specialized nurses, social workers, and others) and to the allotment of financial resources (centers providing medical attention, laboratories, imaging facilities, medicines, etc.) that are necessary for the treatment the children [14].

Conclusion: The pattern of childhood cancer in Iraq is slightly different from the patterns in other countries. Higher frequency of leukemias than most other countries.

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Figure (1): The pattern of childhood countries in 4 countries.